

The role of artificial contact materials in experimental use-wear studies: a controlled proxy to understand use-wear polish formation

Lisa Schunk¹⁻³, Walter Gneisinger², Ivan Calandra², João Marreiros²⁻⁴

¹Institute for Archaeology, Faculty of Historical and Pedagogical Sciences, University of Wrocław, Poland

²TraCEr, Laboratory for Traceology and Controlled Experiments at MONREPOS Archaeological Research Centre and Museum for Human Behavioural Evolution, RGZM, Neuwied, Germany

³Institute for Prehistoric and Protohistoric Archaeology, Johannes Gutenberg University, Mainz, Germany

⁴ICArEHB, Interdisciplinary Center for Archaeology and Evolution of Human Behaviour, University of Algarve, Faro, Portugal

Corresponding author: lisa.schunk@rgzm.de

Keywords

Controlled experiment - surface texture analysis – traceology – contact material – variable control – standardisation - ethics

Highlights

- Cutting movement on natural as well as on artificial contact material led to the development of use-wear traces
- Hard contact material has more impact on the change in surfaces roughness compared to soft contact material
- When the tool surface gets abraded, the surface does not necessarily get smoother; surface roughness can also increase
- Both, tool use intensity/duration and tool raw material properties highly affect wear formation
- The use of artificial contact material offers various advantages (ethical aspects etc.)

Abstract

Traceological studies aim at the recognition and the identification of use-wear traces on artefacts to gain a functional interpretation of past human technologies. However, the development of use-wear traces is known to be dependent on different mechanics involved, such as those related to the contact materials, but also to the tool raw material and morphology, the use intensity and the performed task. Therefore, an understanding of the fundamental mechanics affecting wear formation is necessary to build reliable interpretations based on causation.

The cause-effect relationship between individual variables and the formation of use-wear can only be investigated by conducting controlled, second-generation experiments. To test individual variables, others have to be standardised. This applies, for instance, to the contact material.

The here presented sequential second-generation experiment tested for differences between soft and hard contact materials. Simultaneously, this experiment aimed to validate

44 the comparability of artificial and natural contact material as a standardised substitute, but
45 also as an ethically more acceptable choice. Combined with qualitative and quantitative use-
46 wear analyses, the data generated throughout the experiment did not only provide insights
47 into the development of use-wear, but also into abrasion processes within the experimental
48 setup. Concerning these aspects, no significant difference between the natural and artificial
49 contact materials could be observed. Consequently, while not used as direct proxies to
50 interpret wear on archaeological artefacts, the use of standardised contact materials can be
51 an advantageous choice in controlled experimental setups. Moreover, the experiment
52 highlights the relevance of use intensity and duration in the context of wear formation.

53

54 **1. Introduction**

55 Traceological analyses try to answer questions about how past artefacts were produced,
56 used and altered. When studying the use of stone tools, the goal is to identify the performed
57 movement and the material the tool was in contact with through the traces of use. Such
58 functional interpretations imply the reliable identification of the variables likely to be
59 involved in the development of use-wear. Variables include the performed task and the
60 properties of the contact material, as well as the raw material properties, tool morphology
61 and use intensity and/or duration (Hayden, 1979; Keeley, 1980). During the last couple of
62 decades, use-wear analysis as a sub-discipline of archaeology has undergone several
63 changes, including methodological developments, theoretical and conceptual shifts (Grace,
64 1996; Evans et al., 2014; Stemp et al., 2016; Macdonald et al., 2018; Marreiros et al., 2020
65 for reviews). One of these developments is the integration of quantitative surface
66 characterisation techniques such as focus variation microscopy (Macdonald, 2014; Pflöging
67 et al., 2019; Stemp et al., 2019; Macdonald et al., 2020) and confocal microscopy (e.g. Evans
68 and Donahue, 2008; Stemp and Chung, 2011; Giusca et al., 2012; Stemp et al., 2013; Evans et
69 al. 2014; Macdonald et al. 2018; Stemp et al. 2019; Álvarez-Fernández et al., 2020; Bradfield,
70 2020; Martisius et al., 2020; Pederagnana et al., 2020a, b) coupled with surface metrology
71 software (d’Errico and Backwell, 2009; Sahle et al., 2013; Ibáñez et al., 2019; Martisius et al.,
72 2018; Calandra et al., 2019 a, b , c). Based on this quantitative approach, standardised
73 criteria for the variability within and between different types of use-wear can be defined.
74 This way, while the quantitative approach supports and complements a qualitative use-wear
75 analysis, it also allows to explore in more detail aspects such as sub-types of traces within
76 the so-called “families of wear traces” (e.g. Ibáñez et al., 2019; Marreiros et al., 2020).

77 Most quantitative use-wear studies have been applied on experimental replicas with the aim
78 to improve the identification and discrimination of the contact material (Evans and Donahue,
79 2008; González-Urquijo and Ibáñez-Estévez, 2003; Evans and MacDonald, 2011; Pederagnana
80 and Ollé, 2017; Martisius et al., 2018; Ibáñez et al., 2019; Álvarez-Fernández et al., 2020;
81 Pederagnana et al., 2020a). While these studies have successfully shown that different
82 worked materials correlate with distinct wear traces, how and when these traces form is still
83 only vaguely understood. However, this information has crucial implications on the
84 interpretation of aspects such as use duration and the performed movement. Thus, if the
85 goal is to understand the role of the contact material in the formation process of use-wear,

86 then experiments should be conducted under controlled conditions, as would be the case for
87 highly controlled, second-generation experiments (sensus Marreiros et al., 2020). The
88 “human factor” (i.e. variability), as well as subjectivity (e.g. applied force), is reduced to a
89 minimum by the use of a mechanical device. The high level of control in a second-generation
90 experiment allows for focussing on basic fundamental mechanics by testing and measuring
91 the effect of individual variables. Additionally, aspects such as tool functionality, efficiency or
92 tool use duration can be addressed, allowing to infer human behaviour. When performed
93 sequentially (Stemp and Stemp, 2003; Ollé and Vergès, 2014; Pedergrana and Ollé, 2017;
94 Ibáñez and Mazzucco, 2021), such second-generation experiments allow for investigating the
95 mechanics of use-wear formation. This also means, highly controlled experiments do not
96 function for reproducing archaeological findings. Instead, by conducting second-generation
97 experiments, physical and mechanical causalities can be investigated. To test individual
98 variables within an experimental setup, others have to be standardised (Eren et al., 2016; Lin
99 et al., 2018; Marreiros et al., 2020).

100 The use of modern material substitutes is not uncommon in experimental design due to
101 their inherent advantages (e.g. Dibble and Pelcin, 1995; Dibble and Rezek, 2009; Iovita et al.,
102 2014, 2016; Key et al., 2018; Kranioti et al., 2019; Dogandžić et al., 2020; Eren et al., 2022).
103 The artificial materials used in this study are modern substitutes, produced in bulk and
104 therefore uniform and standardised to match given specifications. Thus, they improve data
105 reproducibility and internal experimental validity (Eren et al., 2017; 2022). Furthermore,
106 they are an ethically more acceptable choice as a substitute for materials derived from
107 animals and/or endangered species. Artificial materials also alleviate any health and safety
108 issues arising when experimenting with biological material, especially over extended periods
109 of time. On the contrary, the high degree of standardisation and the uniformity of modern
110 samples reduce the effects inferred by unknown variables encountered in natural samples,
111 e.g., due to their structure or composition. Consequently, results need to be viewed with
112 caution, making it initially necessary to detach results from the interpretation of the
113 archaeological record.

114 The here presented sequential second-generation experiment tested for differences in wear
115 formation between hard and soft contact materials as one independent variable. To do so,
116 as many inhomogeneous variables as possible were standardised. Besides the sensor-
117 monitored mechanical device, standardised, machine-cut samples made of two different raw
118 materials were used. With the aim to understand the influence of hard and soft contact
119 material on wear formation on the one hand, and to produce reliable and reproducible data
120 on the other, commercially available, standardised, artificial contact materials were
121 introduced into the experimental design. Thus, the experiment also aimed at validating the
122 comparability of artificial and natural contact materials in studies that address the
123 understanding of the mechanical processes involved in the formation of diagnostic wear
124 traces.

125

126 **2. Material and methods**

127

128 The methods applied within the experiment are described and illustrated in detail in the
129 protocol on protocol.io (<https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.eq2lyn91pvx9/v2>). Thus, the
130 methods and materials described here should be seen as a short summary.

131

132 2.1 Experimental design

133 The experiment was designed (**fig. 1**) with the aim to identify patterns and processes by
134 testing the influence of individual factors within a complex system. Thus, the experimental
135 setup involved a modular mechanical device, the SMARTTESTER® (Calandra et al. 2020; **fig.**
136 **2**). The use of a mechanical device minimised the “human factor” and allows for the
137 reduction of subjectivity and human action bias. The SMARTTESTER® conducts precise,
138 repeatable and sensor-monitored movements. The linear setup (see Calandra et al., 2020)
139 was used to perform unidirectional cutting movements with defined cutting lengths. Three
140 parameters were fixed and monitored during the experiment: peak velocity, acceleration
141 and downward force applied by dead weights mounted on the sample holder. These factors
142 were measured continuously during the experiment and two additional sensors recorded
143 the penetration depth and friction; friction was approximated with a compression load cell
144 fixed between the free running sample stage and a rigid support frame in direction of cutting
145 movement.

146 A sample holder ensured the correct positioning of the experimental samples (described
147 below) during the experiment: Samples were clamped perpendicular to the contact material
148 and any deviating angle was corrected to ensure parallel alignment of the cutting edge with
149 the surface of the contact material. Within the programming of the SMARTTESTER®, a
150 template per sample was created to ensure the constancy of the programmed settings, as
151 for instance the position of the sample on the x-, y- and z-axes.

152 The experiment was conducted sequentially with four cycles totalling 2000 cutting strokes.
153 The first cycle consisted of stroke number 1-50, the second of stroke 51-250, the third of
154 stroke 251-1000 and the final cycle ranged from stroke number 1001-2000.

155

controlled variables

velocity = 600.00 mm/s
 acceleration = 4000.00 mm/s²
 cutting length = 10.00/20.00 cm
 force = 20/60 N

linear cutting movement

●● = Documentation: weight, mould, 3D scan, EDF-stitching image

156
157

Figure 1. Experimental design.

158
 159 **Figure 2.** Experimental setup. Linear drives of the Inotec SMARTTESTER®. Weights totalling 6
 160 kg are attached to the sample holder. An experimental standard sample (here FLT4-15) is
 161 clamped into the sample holder. The cow scapula is horizontally fixed on the table as contact
 162 material.

163

164 2.2 Experimental sample preparation

165 Standardised samples were used in the experiment, which allowed for the exclusion of some
 166 confounding factors in the experimental design. Two materials were chosen: Baltic flint and
 167 silicified schist. The raw material was treated as an independent variable within the
 168 experimental setup. The samples were produced according to the following protocol (**fig. 3**):
 169 Selected raw material nodules were cut into slices with a lapidary slab saw. Raw material
 170 intra-variability was reduced by limiting the number of nodules. Further, the slices were cut
 171 into size-defined blanks. Using a diamond band saw, a unifacial edge angle of 60° was
 172 produced along the width of the blank (= active edge). For a cutting movement, this presents
 173 a relatively high edge angle value but it was chosen to prevent rapid severe edge damage
 174 and material loss since more acute edge angles are more prone to this type of damage. In
 175 addition, the leading side of the active edge was modified again with the diamond band saw,
 176 creating a 45° chamfered edge, with a defined remaining edge length. The idea behind the
 177 chamfered edge was to minimise the risk of immediate fracturing by distributing the forces
 178 applied locally across a larger surface, as soon as contact between sample and contact
 179 material was initiated. In total, 24 experimental standard samples were prepared, 12 flint
 180 and 12 silicified schist samples. In an effort to economise on blank production and to reduce
 181 raw material intra-variability, cut blades were “recycled” after half of the samples (i.e., 12
 182 blades) had been used experimentally: the first ~10 mm of the active edge were removed
 183 from each used sample as “slices” with the diamond band saw and 12 new samples could be
 184 produced this way, keeping the previously used active edge segment for subsequent
 185 analysis.

186

187
 188 **Figure 3.** Standard sample production. The raw pieces (a; here Baltic flint) are cut into blanks
 189 (b) with a lapidary slab saw. A diamond band saw was used to cut the blank to create a
 190 typical standard sample with a defined edge angle (c) and a 45° chamfered edge. Highlighted
 191 are the three beads used as coordinate system (see Calandra et al., 2019c). The red dotted
 192 line indicates where the samples are cut after they have been used to “recycle” the blank
 193 and to reveal a new surface.

194
 195 As part of the sample preparation protocol, a cleaning procedure was applied. A rinse in tap
 196 water was followed by cleaning in a preheated ultrasonic bath. The samples were packed in
 197 individual plastic bags filled with ~ 100 ml of demineralised water and non-ionic detergent.
 198 At 45°C and 100 kHz, the samples were left in the ultrasonic bath for 10 min. In a next step,
 199 the detergent solution was exchanged with tap water to rinse off detergent residues in a
 200 first step. This was repeated two more times. The samples were finally rinsed with ~ 100 ml
 201 purified water and air dried.

202 To ensure the possibility of analysing the exact same area of the samples before, between
 203 and after the experiment, a coordinate system was applied directly on the samples’ surfaces
 204 (Calandra et al., 2019c). Three 100-200 µm diameter ceramic beads were adhered with
 205 epoxy resin on the two main surfaces (dorsal and ventral side) of the tool.

206
 207 **2.3 Contact materials**

208 To address the research question, in addition to the raw material, another independent
 209 variable was introduced – the contact materials (**fig. 4**). Both extremes were tested: hard
 210 and soft contact material, presented as natural and as soft artificial substitutes. Therefore, a
 211 fresh cow scapula (*Bos primigenius*) and fresh pig skin (*Sus scrofa domesticus*) were selected.
 212 The reasons for choosing a cow scapula can be explained by the size and shape. The
 213 morphology of the bone offers the possibility to perform long cutting strokes on a relatively
 214 straight surface, providing better conditions for a comparison of the results with the other
 215 tested contact materials. It was provided by a butcher in a fresh state. The periosteum and
 216 small pieces of flesh were still attached to the bone. The cutting experiment was carried out
 217 in a laboratory under ambient room temperature conditions. Two pieces of natural pig skin
 218 were also provided by a butcher by separating the skin from the flesh below. Experiments on
 219 the skin were conducted on the SMARTTESTER® at room temperature; overnight the
 220 mounted skin was kept cold in a fridge. Within this experiment, the cow scapula and the pig

221 skin present the natural contact material. As a second category, artificial contact material
222 was used and tested as an equivalent to the natural materials. Artificial generic bone plate
223 made of modified bone-like polyurethane coated with a rubber skin imitating the
224 periosteum, was used (SYNBONE®). In the experimental application, this served as an
225 artificial equivalent to a fresh, defleshed bone. As artificial skin, a SYNBONE® soft tissue pad
226 with a matrix was used. This skin pad is made of “ecoflex” silicone.
227

228
229 **Figure 4.** Contact materials: natural cow scapula and artificial bone plate (left); natural pig
230 skin and artificial soft tissue pad (right).
231

232 2.4 Sample documentation

233 As a raw material property, the hardness of the two involved rock types – flint and silicified
234 schist – was measured. Hardness was acquired on the experimental blanks with a Leeb
235 rebound hardness tester (in HLC), allowing for a rapid and non-destructive test procedure
236 (Rodríguez-Rellán, 2016; Corkum et al., 2018). The Leeb rebound hardness test requires
237 certain sample properties (mass, size, surface roughness and slopes). While the experimental
238 samples provide ideal flat and smooth surfaces, they do not fulfil the minimum size
239 requirement. Therefore, an additional stable supporting base was used. The samples were
240 placed on the base and connected with a layer of reversible coupling paste. To estimate
241 intra-sample variability, each sample was measured ten times, each time at a different
242 location.

243 The experimental standard samples were documented before and after each sequential
244 cycle following an identical protocol. This protocol consists of four steps: weighing, 3D
245 scanning, documentation with a digital microscope and preparation of silicone moulds of the

246 active edges. The samples' weight was measured with a weighing scale. With a structured-
247 light scanner, the experimental samples were scanned using a S-150 field of view (FOV).
248 Based on the 3D models, for instance changes in volume and in the edge angle can be
249 calculated. The samples were visually documented with a digital microscope (ZEISS
250 Smartzoom 5). Three of the four surfaces per samples (one lateral and the two main
251 surfaces) were documented with a PlanApo D 1.6x/0.10 objective. In a final step, moulds of
252 the edge of the two main surfaces were taken after cleaning the samples' surfaces with 2-
253 propanol 70 % v/v. The treatment with alcohol, however, was not sufficient for the samples
254 used on the fresh cow scapula. Thus, these samples were cleaned following an additional
255 cleaning protocol. The presence of mainly lipids and collagen in addition to abraded mineral
256 particulates was considered to act as binder with adhesive properties. Therefore, a cleaning
257 agent containing enzymes such as lipase and protease was used in preference to acids or
258 alkalis requiring subsequent neutralisation. After cleaning, the respective samples were
259 analysed with a SEM coupled with an EDX detector (ZEISS EVO 25 + Bruker Quantax XFlash
260 6|30M) to verify the absence of residues (see **Supplementary data 1**). As a moulding
261 material, Provil® novo light regular was used. Subsequently, a second moulding material was
262 used, AccuTrans AB. Qualitative and quantitative use-wear analysis was conducted on
263 (mainly) the moulds of all 24 experimental samples. For reasons of consistency, use-wear
264 analysis only refers to data from the side of the standard samples cut with the lapidary slab
265 saw. Use-wear analysis was carried out on all samples before the first and after the last
266 cycle of the experiment. An additional systematic sampling led to the selection of eight (i.e.
267 four flint and four silicified schist samples) out of the total 24 experimental samples for a
268 microscopic analysis of the cycles in between. Each of the four samples per raw material was
269 tested on a different contact material: bone cow scapula, bone plate, pig skin and skin pad.
270 The qualitative use-wear analysis was carried out in a high-power approach by means of an
271 upright light microscope (ZEISS Axio Scope.A1 MAT). The samples were studied using EC-
272 Epiplan 5x/0.13, 10x/0.25 and 20x/0.40 objectives. Traces were documented as an EDF black
273 and white image. The acquisition for quantitative use-wear analysis was executed with a
274 laser-scanning confocal microscope (ZEISS Axio Imager.Z2 Vario + ZEISS LSM 800 MAT). The
275 objective C Epiplan-Apochromat 50x/0.95 was generally used. In a few cases, the C Epiplan-
276 Apochromat 20x/0.70 was chosen, because the small working distance of the 50x objective
277 (0.22 mm) made it virtually impossible to image the sample. The FOV was 255.56 x 255.56
278 µm or 638.9 x 638.9 µm, respectively. Each sample was measured three times at nearby, but
279 non-identical spots. These scans are treated as replicas and verify the level of homogeneity
280 within each trace. Additional wide field black and white EDF images were taken with the C
281 Epiplan- Apochromat 10x/0.40 and 20x/0.70 objectives.

282

283 2.5 Data processing for quantitative use-wear analysis

284 The data acquired with the confocal microscope was processed in batch with different
285 templates in ConfoMap (a derivative of MountainsMap Imaging Topography developed by
286 Digital Surf, Besançon, France; version ST 8.1.9286. Details about the templates can be found
287 in the protocol (<https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.eq2lyn91pvx9/v2>). The ConfoMap

288 templates for each surface in MNT and PDF formats are available on Zenodo
289 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7229779>). This also includes all original and processed
290 surfaces, as well as the results.

291 All descriptive analyses (summary statistics, scatter plots and principal component analysis)
292 were performed in the open-source software R version 4.0.2 through RStudio version
293 1.3.1073 (RStudio Inc., Boston, USA) for Microsoft Windows 10. Reports of the analysis in
294 HTML format, created with knitr v. 1.29 and rmarkdown v. 2.3 are available on Zenodo
295 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7229814>). The raw data, the scripts and the RStudio project
296 are also saved in the same repository.

297

298 **3. Results**

299 3.1 General results

300 All 24 experimental standard samples completed the four cycles with a total of 2000 cutting
301 strokes each. The samples experienced minimal material loss. Thus, none of the samples lost
302 their functionality over time.

303

304 3.2 Leeb rebound hardness data

305 Based on the tested samples, flint is harder than silicified schist (**fig. 5**). The arithmetic mean
306 for the flint is 960 HLC while the one from silicified schist is 903 HLC. The variability in HLC
307 for silicified schist is considerably higher compared to flint: flint hardness ranges from 944
308 HLC to 969 HLC, while the range for the silicified schist is 786 – 966 HLC. Hardness is just one
309 raw material property that makes silicified schist different from flint. Silicified schist is a raw
310 material characterised by fine layers (schistosity) and small cracks. When the impact body of
311 the Leeb rebound hardness tester hits a less compact area of the surface (e.g. a crack
312 underneath the surface), rebound energy gets dissipated and the Leeb hardness value will
313 be smaller. This will be more frequently the case for the silicified schist than for flint.

314

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Figure 6. Examples of use-wear after 2000 unidirectional cutting strokes. The images are taken with a ZEISS Axio Scope.A1 MAT with a 20x objective. The images 1a-d show silicified schist samples, images 2a-d flint samples. The samples were used a) on pig skin, b) on the skin pad, c) on cow scapula and d) on bone plate.

332 The results of the quantitative use-wear analysis underline the findings from the qualitative
 333 use-wear analysis: the use of the soft contact materials has less of an effect on the surface of
 334 the tool than the hard contact materials. This becomes evident when plotting the data
 335 analysed according to the ISO 25178-2 parameters (21 ISO + SSFA parameters; see
 336 **Supplementary data 2**; International Organization for Standardization, 2012). To explain the
 337 data in more detail, individual parameters serve as representatives in place of the others.
 338 One of them is Sq, an amplitude parameter belonging to the areal field parameters. Sq is a
 339 measure of surface roughness, expressing the root mean squared height. Simply said, the
 340 higher the Sq value, the higher the surface roughness. With the aim to understand whether
 341 there is a trend towards an increase or decrease in surface roughness on the experimental
 342 samples after use, the mean value of the three measurements per sample was calculated
 343 and the difference from 0 to after 2000 cutting strokes was computed (**fig. 7**). For the
 344 samples used on the soft contact materials the amplitude of change is really small (**fig. 8**).
 345 However, there is no clear trend visible. For instance, the silicified schist samples show in
 346 four cases a (minimal) decrease in surface roughness and in two a slight increase. The results
 347 for the flint samples are similar. Other parameters from different categories were
 348 considered too (see **Supplementary data 3**). Among them are Vmc as volume parameter, as
 349 well as Asfc, HAsfc9 and epLsar as three fractal analysis parameters. The results for these
 350 parameters do not differ considerably from Sq and thus no significant differences between
 351 the samples used on soft natural and artificial contact materials can be pointed out. This is
 352 slightly different for the hard contact material. Generally, the use of the bone has more
 353 impact on the samples' surface than the other tested materials. While the use of bone
 354 increases the Sq value, the opposite is true for the bone plate.
 355

356

357 **Figure 7.** Mean Sq value of the three taken measurements per sample calculated according
 358 to the ISO 25178-2. The plot shows the difference from 0 to 2000 cutting strokes on the hard
 359 contact materials.
 360

361
 362 **Figure 8.** Mean Sq value of the three measurements taken per sample calculated according
 363 to the ISO 25178-2. The plot shows the difference from 0 to 2000 cutting strokes on the soft
 364 contact materials.
 365

366 To test the data further, a PCA was performed as descriptive statistics. The PCA was applied
 367 on seven selected parameters. These parameters are Sq, Ssk, Vmc, Mean density of furrows,
 368 Isotropy, Asfc and HAsfc9, spanning the different categories of field, SSFA and texture
 369 direction parameters. The PCA (**fig. 9**) reflects the variance between the samples used on the
 370 four contact materials separated into flint and silicified schist samples. For the flint, Principal
 371 component 1 (PC1) reflects 48.08 % of the variance and is correlated with Sq, Vmc, and Asfc.
 372 The variance in Ssk, Mean density of furrows, Isotropy and HAsfc9 is represented by Principal
 373 Component 2 (PC2), which accounts for 16.98 %. PC1 and PC2 values differ slightly for
 374 silicified schist with 48.05 % and 21.03 %, respectively. The data does not cluster in groups;
 375 instead, the data points from the four contact materials overlap, especially concerning the
 376 silicified schist samples. The data points from the flint samples seem to cluster slightly with
 377 the tendency of a separation between bone plate and the other contact materials.
 378

379
 380 **Figure 9.** Principal component analysis applied to the measurements taken on flint (top) and
 381 silicified schist (bottom) standard samples after 2000 cutting strokes, reflecting variation
 382 regarding the contact material.

383
 384 **3.4 Use-wear formation**

385 The eight microscopically analysed samples studied after each cycle, provide information
 386 about the timing of the wear formation (**fig. 10, 11**). The soft contact material led to a slower
 387 formation compared to the hard material. However, the marginally developed traces can be
 388 correlated with the limited penetration depth into the contact materials. Both samples
 389 (FLT4-4 and LYDIT4-1) used on the fresh pig skin developed microscopically visible use-wear
 390 during the last cycle between 1000 and 2000 cutting strokes. By contrast, the samples tested
 391 on the fresh cow scapula developed use-wear earlier. In the case of the flint sample (FLT4-

392 15), use-wear appeared after the second cycle (250 strokes), whereas traces of use-wear on
393 the lydite sample (LYDIT 4-5) were already visible after the first cycle (50 strokes). An
394 identical temporal development of the use-wear traces can be noted for the samples used
395 on the artificial contact material (FLT4-7 and LYDIT4-2). Thus, the samples used on the hard
396 natural contact material developed use-wear traces earlier than the ones used on the hard
397 artificial contact material. Concerning the soft contact material, this difference is
398 qualitatively not noticeable. Moreover, the use of both hard contact materials has more
399 impact on silicified schist samples than on flint samples.

400 The quantitative use-wear analysis conducted after each cycle on the selected eight samples
401 shows that the development of use-wear on the experimental samples is a dynamic process,
402 evolving throughout the course of the experiment. However, measured on the calculated
403 parameters, the surface is not changing continuously into one direction. The use of the soft
404 contact material for instance has less impact on the surface than the hard material, as
405 mentioned earlier. Nevertheless, in contact with the pig skin, the surface of the flint and
406 silicified schist sample seems to alter. Taking Sq as an example (**fig. 12**), surface roughness
407 increases in case of the silicified schist sample after 50 strokes to decrease within the
408 following cycles again. The flint shows the same pattern, but a significant decrease does not
409 occur before 1000 strokes. Similar surface effects can be noticed with the samples used on
410 hard contact materials. This pattern is particularly visible on the samples tested on the cow
411 scapula. Taking Sq as an example again, surface roughness increases significantly during the
412 experiment on both flint and silicified schist and decreases in the case of silicified schist
413 sample after 250 strokes. Interestingly, and corresponding to the qualitative use-wear
414 analysis, surface texture modification seems to take place earlier on silicified schist than on
415 flint.

416

417 **4. Discussion**

418 The identification of use-wear traces is known to be dependent on different mechanics
419 involved, such as those related to the contact material, but also the tool raw material and
420 morphology, the use intensity and the performed task (e.g. Lerner, et al., 2007; Giusca et al.,
421 2012; Pedergnana and Ollé, 2017; Martisius et al., 2018; Ibáñez et al., 2019; Álvarez-
422 Fernández et al., 2020; Ibáñez and Mazzucco, 2021). This multitude of possible influencing
423 variables renders a functional interpretation of past human technologies complicated, but
424 not impossible. Prerequisite for a reliable interpretation is a clear understanding of the
425 cause-effect relationships between individual variables. No less important is the
426 understanding of use duration in these relationships. The presented sequential second-
427 generation experiment tested for the effect of hard and soft contact material on wear
428 formation. For this reason, a natural cow scapula and pig skin has been tested in comparison
429 to artificial equivalents – a bone plate and a soft tissue pad.

430

431
 432 **Figure 10.** Use-wear development on silicified schist samples throughout the experiment.
 433 The images are taken with a ZEISS Axio Scope.A1 MAT using a 10x objective.
 434

435
 436 **Figure 11.** Use-wear development on flint samples throughout the experiment. The images
 437 are taken with a ZEISS Axio Scope.A1 MAT using a 10x objective.

438 The cutting movement performed on natural as well as on artificial contact material led to
439 the development of use-wear over time. The amplitude of change is smaller for the soft
440 contact materials. This means, hard contact material has a greater capacity to lead to surface
441 texture modifications. At the same time, the use of natural contact materials seemed to
442 favour wear formation in comparison to the tested artificial contact materials when
443 considering the quantitative data only. While some contact materials as for instance antler,
444 bone and ivory as one category, or especially cereals as another leave distinguishable and
445 identifiable use-wear traces (Stemp, 2014; Ibáñez et al., 2014; Ibáñez et al., 2016;
446 Pedergrana et al., 2020; Ibáñez and Mazzucco, 2021; Rodriguez et al., 2021), others such as
447 meat and hide do not. Correspondingly, the study shows that the visual appearance of the
448 use-wear traces on experimental samples differs for the soft and hard contact materials (**fig.**
449 **6**). Based on the qualitative assessment, the use-wear traces of natural as well as artificial
450 contact materials appear to be comparable. However, the natural cow scapula led more
451 intense surface abrasions than the artificial equivalent. The results suggest that not only the
452 hardness of the contact material is of relevance, but also structural properties such as the
453 heterogeneity and its condition (e.g. fresh vs. dry), which is where natural and artificial
454 equivalents may differ significantly (e.g. the presence of lubricants in natural fresh
455 materials). While structural homogeneity in natural contact materials can likely not be
456 reached, varying conditions are known to affect use-wear formation (e.g. Buc, 2011; Zhilin,
457 2017; Thun Hohenstein et al., 2020; Martisius, 2022). Further experimental studies focusing
458 on the variation in contact materials, including their conditions, are inevitable to address
459 use-wear in that concern.

460 The results of the quantitative use-wear analysis confirm the textural changes of the micro
461 surface after 2000 cutting strokes, associated with visual polish formation and underlining
462 the benefits of a combined qualitative and quantitative use-wear analysis. Interestingly, the
463 analysis of the samples after each sequential cycle highlights the dynamic nature of the use-
464 wear formation process. The surface changes are not reflected in a continuous increase or
465 decrease of the calculated parameters, instead, these processes alternate over time. In their
466 experimental study Ibáñez and Mazzucco (2021) documented a continuous wear
467 development based on qualitative and quantitative data towards a decrease in surface
468 roughness. However, the experimental samples constitute one crucial difference between
469 both experiments. While Ibáñez and Mazzucco used knapped samples, due to the defined
470 research questions and goals, the presented study is based on machine-cut experimental
471 standard samples. It should be noted that the experimental standard samples are not to be
472 compared to knapped samples or intended to replicate a natural surface. Instead, the use of
473 these samples creates a comparable framework by reducing variability and thus, eliminating
474 an influencing factor. Hence, the machine-cut surface appears rather polished due to the use
475 of a lapidary slab saw and a fine-grained diamond band saw and differs from natural
476 (knapped) surfaces. This means, relating to the results from Ibáñez and Mazzucco, the initial
477 surface of the experimental samples likely influences the outcome.

478 With the exception of sample LYDIT4-2 and LYDIT4-11, the resulting surface texture
479 modification is at first equal to an increase in surface roughness, as expressed by the Sq

480 parameter. In the following cycle, this trend was reversed and the surface roughness
481 decreased. Again, these observations are assumed to be correlated with the initial surface
482 texture of the experimental samples. The first rapid increase in surface roughness
483 documented on most samples could be explained with initial abrasion processes (Schmidt et
484 al., 2020) removing the surface created by the saws and leading to a temporary state of a
485 more “natural” surface. The subsequent decrease in surface roughness is in accordance with
486 the data from other similar studies (Ibáñez and Mazzucco, 2021; see also Rodriguez et al.,
487 2021).

488 Furthermore, the assumption that the initial surface roughness plays an important role
489 becomes evident when comparing the results of the two sample raw materials involved. In
490 comparison to silicified schist, flint is the harder raw material, as shown (**Fig. 12**). At the
491 same time, flint has a lower surface roughness. Based on the measurements taken of the
492 standard samples before the experiment was conducted, the mean Sq value for flint is 918.5
493 nm, while the value for silicified schist is 1786.6 nm. Data shows that the formation of use-
494 wear did not progress at the same rate for both raw materials (Stemp and Stemp 2003).
495 Polish as surface texture modification developed more rapidly on silicified schist. Flint
496 needed to be used more intensively for the surface to be affected. The data indicates that
497 the two aspects, raw material hardness and surface roughness, likely play a significant role
498 concerning surface texture modification. A surface with a higher surface roughness seems
499 more prone to abrasion processes than an equivalent one with a lower surface roughness.
500 The same can be said for raw materials with a lower hardness compared to harder raw
501 materials. Nevertheless, it remains unclear, whether use-wear formation on silicified schist
502 and flint progresses through the same stages. The data suggests that this could be the case
503 (**fig. 13**), especially when considering the before mentioned decrease in surface roughness
504 after an increase. These observations emphasise the need of raw material characterisation in
505 functional analyses as one variable involved (e.g. Lerner, 2007; Lerner et al., 2007; Lerner,
506 2014; Pedernana and Ollé, 2017; Marreiros et al., 2020). Otherwise, questions related to
507 tribological aspects including fracture mechanics and abrasion processes (Schmidt et al.,
508 2020) will not be answered.

509

510
 511 **Figure 12.** Quantitative use-wear development on samples used on hard (top) and soft
 512 (bottom) contact materials. Sq as a parameter was calculated according to ISO 25178-2.

513
 514 Based on the data from this experiment, the crucial impact of use intensity or duration on
 515 wear formation becomes evident. Measurements taken before and after each cycle highlight
 516 the complementary nature of qualitative and quantitative data. Initial surface modifications

517 are barely or not at all visible, but quantifiable. Results indicate that changes on the samples’
 518 micro surface texture are more visible during the first cycles (Ibáñez and Mazzucco, 2021)
 519 according to the quantitative measurements. Perhaps due to the machine-cut surfaces of
 520 the experimental standard samples, the processes and resulting patterns of surface texture
 521 modifications are complex, making it nearly impossible to determine the cycle based on the
 522 quantitative data. Especially for samples used on soft contact material, this problem is also
 523 known for samples with a natural, knapped surface (Ibáñez and Mazzucco, 2021; Rodriguez
 524 et al., 2021). Depending on the stage of development, worked material can only be
 525 identified with a low degree of confidence due to the problem of similar surface
 526 characteristics and thus an overlap of unused and used areas. At the same time, use-wear
 527 can also appear as quantitatively identical after the use of different contact materials at
 528 different stages (see LYDIT4-1 (50 strokes) and LYDIT4-7 (1000 strokes) as an example; **fig.**
 529 **12**). These aspects make it difficult to discriminate functional traces and simultaneously hard
 530 to identify the use duration based on either qualitative or quantitative data solely.
 531

532 **Figure 13.** Quantitative use-wear development on samples used on pig skin and cow scapula.
 533 Sq as a parameter was calculated according to ISO 25178-2. The black dotted lines indicate a
 534 hypothetical trend how Sq could develop on a flint in case the samples would be used
 535 further.
 536

537
 538 With the aim to address use-wear formation processes of different types of traces as well as
 539 the mechanical fracture principles behind the processes, variable control needs to be
 540 considered in experimental design, at least in a first step (**fig. 14**). The mechanical
 541 understanding of wear formation processes will build the basis for archaeological

542 applications and interpretations of the various types of evidence observed on artefacts.
543 Artificial contact material can function as a standardised, controlled proxy for a specific
544 material property. Even though the surface texture modification seems slightly weaker when
545 hard artificial instead of natural contact material is used, the cause-effect relationship is still
546 comparable. Thus, artificial contact material leads to reproducible results and allows for
547 pattern recognition in use-wear formation.
548

ARCHAEOLOGY-LIKE APPROACH

SUPPLEMENTARY STANDARDISED APPROACH

SUITABLE FOR DOCUMENTING / UNDERSTANDING / INVESTIGATING:

non-standardised material

use-wear interpretation

- identification of diagnostic use-wear traces
- building a reference collection
- combining tool design and function

standardised material

use-wear formation

- pattern recognition (e.g. distribution)
- parameter material pairing (e.g. hardness, surface roughness, toughness, condition)
- parameter tool use (e.g. movement, force, velocity, duration)

BUILDING A CAUSALITY MODEL

archaeological material

550 **Figure 14.** Application of an archaeological-like experimental approach compared to a
551 supplementary standardised experimental approach. Illustration by Nicole Viehöver.

552

553 **5. Conclusions**

554 Reconstructing past stone tool use aims at understanding early hominin behavioural
555 dynamics. While the study of traces left on the artefacts' surface after use can provide
556 evidence for the contact material and the performed movement, the understanding of the
557 formation processes of the different types of use-wear traces holds further potential. These
558 data can contribute to the reconstruction of other crucial aspects such as the intensity of
559 use, the condition of the contact material, and ultimately improve the recognition of
560 diagnostic wear patterns. The sequential experiment presented in this paper aimed at
561 investigating use-wear formation on two different raw materials when unidirectional cutting
562 movements were performed on hard as well as on soft contact materials. Simultaneously,
563 artificial contact materials were tested as a controlled proxy within the experimental design.
564 It could be demonstrated that the use of the different contact materials involved led to the
565 development of wear traces over time. Hard contact material causes surface texture
566 modifications more intensively compared to soft contact material. Based on the quantitative
567 data, the use of the natural hard contact material seemed to favour wear formation in
568 comparison to the artificial equivalent. Additionally, the following observation could be
569 made: use-wear formation is highly dependent on the initial surface texture of the samples
570 itself as well as on use intensity or duration. To better understand the implications of the
571 observations mentioned, additional sequential studies are needed in the future. With the
572 aim to discriminate the character of the different types and sub-types of use-wear and to
573 create a framework for reliable functional interpretations, it is indispensable to scrutinise
574 the abrasive processes, including fracture mechanics, responsible for the formation of use-
575 wear. Thus, controlled experiments are unavoidable to prove the causality of relationships.
576 To implement variable control, standardised, artificial contact material can be used, allowing
577 for reproducible results, as well as more ethical experimentations. This study highlights the
578 complementary character of qualitative and quantitative use-wear analyses.

579

580 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

581 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
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583

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597

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